

Use Cases for Obstacle Detection and Track Intrusion Detection Systems in the Context of New-generation of Traffic Management Systems

Cristian Ulianov
Future Mobility Research Group
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne, the UK
cristian.ulianov@ncl.ac.uk

Paul Hyde
Future Mobility Research Group
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne, the UK
paul.hyde@ncl.ac.uk

Jin Liu*
Future Mobility Research Group
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne, the UK
jin.liu@ncl.ac.uk

Abstract— In this paper, the identification and description of use cases for Obstacle Detection and Track Intrusion Detection (OD&TID) systems related to the operation of trains are discussed, with detailed classification, including general cases for mainline railway and specific cases to freight. The identified use cases have been organised with respect to the signalling system condition, Grade of Automation (GoA) levels, various weather conditions and operation modes of the train under control. The use cases are further described, including the system response, actions made by OD&TID system and post-conditions in different scenarios. The priority and complexity of each use case are also discussed with respect to the probability of scenario occurrence and required interfaces. This work has been carried out as part of the process to evaluate implementation constraints, risks and requirements, and the operational scenarios of the OD&TID within the EU-funded Shift2Rail project SMART2, which aims to design and develop a prototype OD&TID system. The system will use on-board and trackside sensors, along with airborne cameras for detecting potential obstacles and/or track intrusion at a distance of up to 2000m ahead of a train, a major focus is on the use of OD & TID for automatic train operation (ATO).

I. INTRODUCTION

The SMART2 project was initiated following on research outputs of a series of previous EU projects. The various operating conditions of OD&TID system were recently studied by ASTRail project of Shift2Rail, which identified suitable technologies for ATO development at different Grade of Automation (GoA) levels [1]. The study discussed the feasibility of applying a detection system for static and moving obstacles near or lying on the track ahead of a moving train, and recommended a sensor-group solution for an on-board OD system. A similar detection system was proposed by Shift2Rail IP5 ARCC project which developed multi-sensor system for rail freight based on existing system developed for trams [2]. Research on OD system was also carried out within the Shift2Rail project SMART, which developed an on-board OD system for freight trains running on mixed mainlines up to 80km/h in all weather conditions [3], that includes several kinds of vision technologies. Based on the SMART project, SMART2 focuses on the detection and classification of obstacles at long range (up to 2km). Furthermore, trackside and airborne OD & TID system are proposed to improve the safety of trains and minimise the risk to the train from intrusion incidents, traffic collision on an adjacent road, etc by detecting them as effectively as possible. To the best of author's knowledge, including the state-of-the-art of railway traffic management system reviewed by Shift2Rail [4], there is few systematic OD & TID systems for ATO in both academia and industry, which makes the research and

delivery of SMART2 project pioneering in the field of railways.

In this paper, we focus on the analysis of key high-level requirements and the use cases (UCs) for an OD&TID system, and the relevance of the SMART2 OD&TID under development to those UCs. The main classification and analysis approaches for generating requirements and UCs are illustrated and discussed.

II. ANALYSIS OF SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS AND USE CASES

A. Requirements Analysis

In order to provide high-level requirements and specification for OD&TID systems, four types of requirements have been considered, analysed and defined: performance, functional, operational and compliance to regulation and standards. All these types of requirements have been divided into three categories:

1. RAM – related to reliability, availability and maintainability,
2. S&S – related to safety and security and
3. Technical – related to the technical characteristics of the system and components.

All the OD & TID requirements are analysed with four features including requirement description, related end-users, related use cases and obligatoriness with respect to SMART2 system. The end-users for SMART2 include infrastructure manager (IM), rail undertaking (RU), rail authority (AUT) and other end-users (OTH).

B. Use Cases for OD & TID System

Considering the UCs at an early stage when designing an OD & TID system is critical in identifying the key actions and event steps to be made by the system. Within the SMART2 project, UCs for the OD & TID system are identified, analysed and classified with two major aspects/criteria: (1) Railway operation type, i.e., UCs relating to general railway traffic those relating specifically to freight operations; (2) different grade of GoA, i.e.: GoA 0-1 and GoA 2-3-4. This resulted in the following nine use cases:

UC ID	Description
General UCs	
GAF-01	Operation on mainline with reduced visibility due to temporary environmental conditions (GoA 0-1)
GAF-02	Operation on mainline sections with poor vision conditions (GoA 0-1)

GAF-03	Operation on mainline sections with specific hazards – reduced visibility due to permanent causes (GoA 0-1)
GAF-04	Operation on mainline sections with specific hazards – constructions sites (GoA 0-1)
GAF-05	All conventional ATO trains on mainline (GoA 2-3-4)
GAF-06	All ATO trains on marshalling yard, depot, or similar controlled environment (GoA 2-3-4)

Freight specific UCs

FS-01	Freight train with long stopping distance operating on mainline (GoA 0-1)
FS-02	Freight train with long stopping distance operating on mainline (GoA 2-3-4)
FS-03	Freight train operating on shunting yard or similar controlled environment (GoA 0-1)

The UCs are defined by specific features which describes the details of each scenario. The features of the UCs include: (1) Scope and brief description; (2) Involved stakeholders; (3) Frequency of use; (4) Pre-conditions; (5) Typical use case implementation; (6) Post-conditions; (7) Post-use scenario; (8) Implementation constraints, risks and requirements; (9) Estimated priority; (10) Assumptions and open issues. Based on the features above, each use case is classified into different grades on (1) priority/importance of implementing; (2) complexity of OD & TID system for the UC; (3) likelihood of implementation in the future; (4) relevance of SMART2 concept to the UC.

C. Analysis results

1. Overall priority/importance of implementing the UCs.

Due to differences in the roles of the OD & TID system in each UC, UCs have been classified into different levels with respect to the importance of the system in the operation of trains and therefore the priority for implementation. The importance is related to the frequency of occurrence of a UC and the safety implications of the occurrence of a UC. The priority/importance of implementing the OD & TID system in each use case is summarised as follows.

Level of priority	Use case
Very high	GAF-01; FS-02
High	GAF-06
Medium-high	FS-01
Medium	GAF-01; GAF-02; GAF-03
Medium-low	GAF-04
Low	FS-03

2. Estimation of complexity of OD & TID system for UCs

The development of the OD & TID system needs to consider the difficulties of applying appropriate sensors and their supporting software, along with the difficulty of the required interfaces with other systems, such as: ATO, ATP, TMS, ETCS, etc. The analysis of the complexity of potential OD & TID system concepts that may be developed for each use case is summarised as follows.

Complexity of OD&TID system	Use case
High-Medium	GAF-05; GAF-06; FS-02
Medium-High	GAF-03; FS-01
Medium	GAF-01; GAF-02; GAF-04
Low-medium	FS-03

3. Likelihood of implementation in the future

The likelihood of future implementation was evaluated considering the system’s characteristics, the bottlenecks related to the development gap between the current and required technologies, interface constraints, and system requirements. The implementation of an OD & TID system is possible and is a potential enabler of increasing the GoA of railway operations, therefore, it is very likely that constraints pertaining to different actors and stakeholders will be resolved in the near future, to enable commercialisation and exploitation of OD & TID systems.

4. Relevance of SMART2 concept to different UC

The SMART2 OD & TID concept may significantly improve the performance of railway operation, overcome the drawbacks and mitigate the risks in the scenarios of some use cases, therefore, the relevance to those UC was evaluated as high. Whereas, in other use cases it is less certain that the functions of SMART2 OD & TID concept would deliver and provide a substantial contribution, therefore, the relevance level was estimated as potential. The relevance of the SMART2 concept to UCs; GAF-01, GAF-02, GAF-03, GAF-04, GAF-05, FS-01, and FS-02 was estimated as High. The SMART2 concept was estimated to be potentially relevant to UCs; GAF-04, GAF-06 and FS-03.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we illustrate and discuss an approach to identify, classify and analyse the requirement and use cases of OD & TID systems in general, and for the SMART2 OD & TID system concept in particular. This approach has been developed and applied in the SMART2 and will be used to better define its focus and prioritise further technical activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ferrari *et al.*, “Survey on Formal Methods and Tools in Railways: The ASTRail Approach,” in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2019, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-18744-6_15.
- [2] F. Tannaro, “Depicted in an example: The environment sensing system. Presentation at the Workshop between Shift2Rail IP5 and SMART2 on Technology Demonstrator TD 5.1.3 (Obstacle detection and Track intrusion detection).” Shift2Rail, 2020.
- [3] D. Ristić-Durrant, D. Nikolić, M. Banić, and D. R. Durrant, “Report on sub-systems conformance testing, Deliverable 2.3 of Shift2Rail project SMART (Smart Automation of Rail Transport),” 2019.
- [4] Shift2Rail, “Shift2Rail ANNUAL WORK PLAN and BUDGET 2019,” Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking, 2019.